

The Role of the 'First Step' State Curriculum in the Preschool Education System

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ABSTRACT: The article examines the existing problems in the preschool education system, ongoing reforms aimed at solving these problems, and the importance of the state program "First Step". The advantages of organizing classes based on interactive methods in PEO are shown.

KEY WORDS: preschool education, preschool age, reforms, education, continuous education, pedagogical process, science, interactive.

INTRODUCTION

It is no exaggeration to say that the pre-school education system is the most important stage in the formation of a person. Because this age of education, although a short period of human life, during this period the child realizes and learns a large percentage of what he has learned throughout his life. This period is the basis for future life.

So what are the problems in this system of educating children at important times in their lives, and how are they being addressed? What is new in the field? What can be expected from the reforms?

There are a number of issues that need to be addressed at this important stage of a child's life. Including:

- Full coverage of preschool children in preschool institutions;
- Organize the educational process in preschool institutions in a way that meets modern requirements;
- Make the lessons interactive and fun.

Pre-school education is the primary link in the system of continuing education, which plays an important role in educating and preparing a healthy and well-rounded person for school. Therefore, our country is systematically working to further develop this area, to create all the conditions for our children. At the same time, the contribution of not only state but also non-state educational institutions in the coverage of children in preschool education is significantly increasing.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In general, since the establishment of the Ministry, the number of preschool institutions has increased from 5,211 to 8,104, and the coverage of children has increased from 27.7% to 61.8%.

The pedagogical process aimed at ensuring the full development of preschool children should be simple, age-appropriate and colorful. The successful implementation of educational work depends on the proper organization of the pedagogical process in preschool education, each type of activity. One of the main tasks of today's educators is to focus on the formation and development of children's worldview in all its aspects, both physical and spiritual.

Adequate material, technical, methodological and methodological assistance is provided to educators by government agencies to carry out these tasks. For example, the "First Step" program for the new preschool education, which will be implemented from 2018, is based on state requirements, and all preschools in the country are familiar with this program. A package of documents containing state and program requirements has been delivered to MTTs in all regions. In addition, for the first time in Uzbekistan, thematic planning programs have been distributed to all.

The main principle of this program, called "First Step", is the first steps of young children involved in the educational process. The main tasks of the "First Step" program:

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- setting requirements for the content and quality of development, education of preschool children;
- Introduction of effective forms and methods of education and upbringing of children on the basis of national, universal and spiritual values;
- Introduction of pedagogical and modern information and communication technologies in the educational process;
- Ensuring the effective integration of education, science and industry for targeted and quality training.

In general, the state requirements state that young children and preschoolers should be developed in five areas.

A key area of children's development	Minor areas of development
1. Physical development and a healthy lifestyle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Large motor skills ➤ fine motor skills ➤ sensomotrics ➤ Healthy lifestyle and safety
2. Socio-emotional development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The concept of "I" ➤ Emotions and their management ➤ Socialization ➤ Communication with adults and peers
3. Speech, communication, reading and writing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Speech and language ➤ Reading skills ➤ Fine motor skills of the fingers
4. Development of the cognitive process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ intellectual-cognitive skills ➤ elementary mathematical skills ➤ research-cognitive and effective reflexive activity
5. Creative development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Artistic imagination of the world ➤ artistic and creative abilities

By developing these five areas, the child develops 4 competencies:

- Physical Development and Healthy Lifestyles competencies;
- Competences in the field of "Social and emotional development";
- Competences in the field of "Speech, communication, reading and writing skills";
- Competences in the field of "Development of the cognitive process";
- Has the competence in the field of "creative development", that is they are motivated to enter 1st grade and are ready for school.

The program is based on the development of the educational process through games. Children develop concepts such as education, creativity, social orientation, a healthy lifestyle, and they begin to understand how to behave in a social environment. Raising preschool children to be curious, active, enterprising, free-thinking, observant, and healthy is an important task for parents and educators. The organization of classes based on advanced pedagogical technologies, using modern, interactive methods that activate children in a comprehensive way, is a very effective factor.

There is a growing interest, attention and demand for improving the effectiveness of education through the use of interactive methods, innovative pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process.

An important aspect of the use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process is the breadth of opportunities for personal development education.

With the use of modern technology, educators need to focus on students to find, independently study and analyze the knowledge they have acquired, and even draw their own conclusions. In this process, the educator creates conditions for the development, formation, acquisition and upbringing of the individual and the community.

At the present stage of development of the education system, pre-school education, which is the first stage of it, is undergoing rapid changes, which are reflected in the following:

- ✓ The legal framework for preschool education is improving;
- ✓ Preschool education institutions are moving to new types of financial and economic activities;
- ✓ The network of non-governmental preschools is expanding; advanced educational technologies are being introduced;
- ✓ The system of staff training is improving;

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- ✓ Introduction of alternative forms of pre-school education on the basis of short-term groups (based on the "Science Way" variable program);
- ✓ Investment projects with the participation of financial institutions are being implemented; Innovative and experimental work in preschool education is gaining momentum.

Today, the rational use of new pedagogical technologies in preschool education creates favorable conditions for linking education to education, to integrate both in terms of structure and content, to integrate the activities of students, to direct them to independent thinking. Classes based on pedagogical technology turn the younger generation into independent-minded, spiritually mature, well-rounded individuals. Therefore, the importance and place of modern teaching methods - interactive methods, innovative technologies in the educational process in educational institutions is invaluable.

Innovation (English innovation - innovation) - means to change the internal structure of the system. Innovation is the relevance of new approaches to a system.

Pedagogical technology is applied on the basis of a systematic approach to education, taking into account the age, mentality, worldview, knowledge, level of activity, goals, directions, content, forms and methods of education. The educator is the organizer of this process, his creative activity is based on his knowledge and skills, the ability to use technical means to influence the interests and aspirations of the child, to achieve guaranteed results using methods that serve to activate the child.

CONCLUSION

In short, a number of reforms are underway in the pre-school education system, all of which are aimed at serving the interests of children and teachers, as well as improving the quality of pre-school education.

In the state program "First Step" and the alternative program "Path of Science", the basis of everything is a social approach, that is, the focus is on the child and his interests. The educator must create a social environment with the parents, the pedagogical staff, the child himself and, of course, social partners such as society and the state.

The interactive methods used by the educator during the lessons, as well as the organization of the children's interests and needs, are an important basis for improving the quality of preschool education.

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